

Understanding Consumer Acceptance of Algae-Based Foods

Why Change What We Eat?

The global food system is under pressure — from climate change to rising health issues. Meat-heavy diets contribute up to 20% of global greenhouse gas emissions. To protect both people and planet, we need to eat differently.

Algae — tiny aquatic plants — offer a powerful solution. They're nutritious, fast-growing, and have a low environmental footprint.

But: are people ready to eat them?

- **Focus:** Sweden, Germany, Finland, Estonia, Lithuania, Norway, Poland
- **Sample size:** 5,250 consumers surveyed

Who Eats What Now?

- **Germany stands out:** 49% are flexitarian, showing a strong shift in eating habits.

Are Eating Habits Changing?

- However, fewer plan to reduce dairy
- Still, algae-based foods are mostly unknown — nearly half never tried them

What Matters Most to Consumers?

- **Taste and enjoyment**
- **Price**
- **Convenience:** Health and sustainability matter — but take a back seat unless the food is tasty, affordable, and easy to prepare.

What do People think about Algae?

Algae is seen as sustainable and healthy — especially when mixed into familiar foods like burgers or fish fingers.

Major consumer concerns about algae-based products include their high cost and limited availability, as well as a lack of familiarity with their taste, texture, and nutritional benefits.

70%
don't recognise common algae names like spirulina

52%
are curious to try algae-based foods

45%
would include the innovative foods in their diet

What Makes Algae-Based Foods Appealing?

Consumers want:

- **Fish alternatives:** fresh, salty, soft and crisp
- **Meat alternatives:** brown, beefy, tender
- **Egg alternatives:** eggy, yellow, creamy — not green or foamy!

Most people prefer products with **<10% algae content** — so algae should be added gradually to food, not as the main ingredient.

Funded by
the European Union

Future Potential

Algae-based foods are trusted more when people know what's in them, how they're made, and what benefits they bring. There's also growing interest in using algae in sustainable textiles like waterproof fabrics.

To grow this market, producers must:

- Improve taste and appearance
- Offer algae in familiar formats
- Make products more affordable and accessible
- Educate and inspire trust

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www.locality-algae.eu